

When DOM is not dependent on the External Argument*

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1. Introduction

This paper is concerned with contexts that exhibit differential object marking (DOM) in the absence of an overt External Argument (EA). The data come from passives and impersonals in three languages with robust DOM, namely (standard) Spanish, Hindi-Urdu and Moldovan (Romanian spoken in the Republic of Moldova). More interestingly, in all these languages, the application of a variety of tests indicates even the absence of an implicit (external) argument (IA) projected in the syntax. Constructions of this type present important interest theoretically; many accounts, both in the descriptive typological and in the formal generative traditions, derive the special morphology in DOM as the result of a need to differentiate subjects from objects, under various instantiations of Burzio's Generalization. Thus, DOM is predicted not to be possible on subjects or in configurations that lack an expressed or at least implicit external argument. What we show instead is that DOM is not dependent on the presence of an EA, given that the latter's being projected in the syntax cannot be unambiguously demonstrated. We propose that there is a type of v which can check accusative Case even if the EA is not merged in Spec, Voice. The differential marker arises on those objects which contain additional discourse-related features, beyond [uC], that need and undergo separate licensing by a head endowed with discourse specifications.

The structure of the paper is as follows. In section 2 we review a range of accounts under which DOM is connected with the presence of the EA and the predictions they make. In section 3 we introduce data from Spanish DOM in passives and impersonals without an overt EA. Through a battery of tests (depictives, reciprocals, etc.) we demonstrate that the syntactic projection of an implicit EA is not motivated either. In section 4 we spell out our analysis, which dissociates DOM from the presence of an implicit EA. In section 5 we turn to passives in Hindi, where similar types of problems are salient. Then, in section 6 we address the so-called impersonal supine in Moldovan, which equally does not give indication of the presence of an implicit EA active in the syntax. Section 7 concludes.

2. DOM and subjects

Many languages present splits in the morpho-syntactic behavior of the direct object, as instantiations of DOM (Comrie 1989; Bossong 1991, 1998; Aissen 2003; de Swart 2007, a.o.). Generally, specifications related to humanness, animacy, specificity, definiteness, etc. trigger

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dedicated marking. A typical example comes from Spanish - the animate definite in (1)a requires a marker which is homophonous with the dative preposition; the inanimate in (1)b, on the other hand, does not permit the same marker (Torrego 1998; López 2012; Fábregas 2013; Ormazabal and Romero 2013, a.o.).

(1) Spanish direct objects¹

- | | | | | | |
|----|-----------------------|-------------|----------|------------|-----------------------------|
| a. | Juan vio | *(a) | la | chica. | |
| | Juan see.PST.3SG | DAT=DOM | DEF.F.SG | girl.F.SG | |
| | 'Juan saw the girl.' | | | | (López 2012: ex. 22a, p.12) |
| b. | Juan vio | (*a) | la | casa. | |
| | Juan see.PST.3SG | DAT=DOM | DEF.F.SG | house.F.SG | |
| | 'Juan saw the house.' | | | | |

Given that DOM is a widespread phenomenon, it has attracted the attention of linguists from various orientations. A well known account comes from the functionalist tradition (based on Comrie 1989 and subseq.). The special morphology in DOM is seen as a disambiguation strategy in those configurations in which objects and subjects are (semantically) too similar. More precisely, it signals those objects that have characteristics more similar to subjects (animacy, etc.) so that the two classes don't get confused.

Incarnations of the subject-object disambiguation hypothesis are also seen in formal generative accounts. For example, under dependent Case analyses (Marantz 1991; Baker 2015; Levin and Preminger 2015, a.o.) the Case feature on special objects (animates, etc.) forces their presence (possibly by raising) into a domain where they enter into Case competition with a higher argument, as in (2); the special morphology of differential objects is derived as a result of the Dependent Case calculus. Unmarked objects (i.e., the inanimate in (1)b) are generally seen as lacking a Case feature, staying unlicensed (Ormazabal and Romero 2013, a.o.)

(2) Dependent Case

Let DP₁ and DP₂ be two nominals in the same domain. If DP₁ c-commands DP₂:

- a. mark DP₁ [= in the clause], ERGATIVE/NOMINATIVE and/or
 b. mark DP₂ [= in the clause], ACCUSATIVE = **DOM** (Baker 2015 adapted, a.o.)

In a somehow similar line, for Richards (2010) DOM is a mechanism to avoid configurations that contain identical elements in an asymmetric c-command relation, which cannot be linearized, as in (3). A problematic linearization statement of the type $\langle \phi P, \phi P \rangle$ is avoided by adding a K head to the special (human, definite, specific, etc.) object; thus, the K layer makes the DOM-ed object structurally distinct.

(3) If a linearization statement $\langle \alpha, \alpha \rangle$ is generated, the derivation crashes (Richards 2010:5)

Other analyses rework the same idea in terms of licensing. For Kalin (2018), DOM is taken to

¹ Abbreviations: ABS = absolutive, ACC = accusative, CL = clitic, DAT = dative, DEF = definite, DOM = differential object marking, ERG = ergative, F = feminine, FUT = future, GEN = genitive, GENR = generic, IMPERS = impersonal, IMPF = imperfective, INF = infinitive, INS = instrumental, LOC = locative, M = masculine, N = neuter, NEG = negative, NOM = nominative, OBL = oblique, PASS = passive, PFV = perfective, PL = plural, PRES = present, PRT = participle, PST = past, RECP = reciprocal, SG = singular, SBJV = subjunctive, SUP = supine.

signal the activation of an additional licenser in the clause. Clauses generally have one licenser, eg. T; subjects are closer to the main licenser and get obligatorily licensed. [uC] on objects with special features (animacy, specificity, etc.) needs the activation of an additional licenser. Under the assumption that DOM is a type of accusative, all these accounts are instantiations of Burzio's Generalization, which blocks the assignment of the accusative case in the absence of a (nominative) subject (Burzio 1986). This hypothesis straightforwardly explains why the (Spanish oblique) differential marker is not possible on the EA/subject of active clauses. As seen in (4), in Spanish no matter whether the subject is animate and definite, it would be ungrammatical with the oblique differential marker.

(4) Spanish EA – no differential marking

(*A)	la	chica	vio	*(a)	Juan.
DAT=DOM	DEF.F.SG	girl.F.SG	see.PST.3SG	DAT=DOM	Juan

Intended: 'The girl saw Juan.'

The case studies we will be discussing here are problematic under these types of accounts. The data of interest involve DOM in passives and impersonals, which do not (and in fact cannot) have an expressed agent counting as the higher nominal. As such, they beg the question whether DOM is indeed to be unified cross-linguistically as depending on the presence of a higher nominal, the subject. A possibility to save Burzio's Generalization is to postulate the presence of an implicit argument in the EA position. What we will be showing is that the syntactic projection of the IA is not straightforward to prove. We start with data from Spanish.

3. Spanish SE passives and impersonals

Another clear prediction of analyses based on Burzio's Generalization is that DOM should not be possible in passive-like configurations. The latter lack an expressed subject and it is normally the theme that raises into the subject's position (possibly also getting nominative case). In many languages, this prediction is indeed borne out. As expected, the so-called periphrastic (*be*) passive in Spanish, constructed with the auxiliary *be* (inflected for person and number) and the past participle (inflected for gender and number), does not allow DOM. The theme must instead be unmarked, no matter whether it is placed preverbally (after promotion to the subject position) or postverbally. This is illustrated in the periphrastic passive in (6)a, where the theme, which in the active counterpart (5) needs obligatory DOM, can only have nominative case and must trigger verb agreement.

Spanish, however, has another passivization-like mechanism, the one constructed with the pronominal-like SE clitic. The latter realizes various types of impersonals, middles and passives, anti-causatives, reflexives, etc.² The surprising fact we are interested in analyzing here is that

² Some Spanish SE contexts are seen below:

- | | | | | | | | |
|------|----------------------------------|--------------|---------------|-----------------|---------------------------|-----------------------|------------------|
| i) | Se | come | muy | bien en Italia. | <i>Impersonal generic</i> | | |
| | SE | eat.PRES.3SG | very | well in Italy | | | |
| | 'One eats very well in Italy.' | | | | | | |
| ii) | Juan | se | lava | todos | los | dias. | <i>Reflexive</i> |
| | Juan | SE | wash.PRES.3SG | all.M.PL | DEF.M.PL | day.PL | |
| | 'Juan washes himself every day.' | | | | | | |
| iii) | El | coche | se | ha | averiado. | <i>Anti-causative</i> | |
| | DEF.M.SG | car | SE | have.PRES.3SG | break down.PST.PRT | | |
| | 'The car broke down.' | | | | | | |

one type of SE *allows* DOM, as in (6)b. Such examples are generally described as having passive and/or impersonal interpretations (see especially Medikoetxea 2008 or Ormazabal and Romero 2013). However, due to the fact the two interpretations might be hard to tell apart,³ we use the SE_{DOM} notation to indicate that this is the type of SE which is possible with differentially marked objects. Note that the sentence in (6)b is grammatical, irrespectively of whether the DOM-ed theme is found preverbally or postverbally. In Spanish, both the (*be*) periphrastic and the SE passive allow a *by*-phrase.

(5) Spanish – DOM in active sentences

El rector felicitó ***(a)** las alumnas.
 DEF.M.SG rector congratulate.PST.3SG DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL
 ‘The rector congratulated the female students.’

(6) Spanish – DOM under passive/impersonal SE

a. Periphrastic passive – DOM not possible

[(*A) las alumnas] fueron felicitadas **[(*a)**
 DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL be.PST.3PL congratulate.PST.PRT.F.PL DAT=DOM
 las alumnas] (por el rector).
 DEF.F.PL student.F.PL (by DEF.M.SG rector)
 Intended: ‘The female students have been congratulated (by the rector).’

b. SE_{PASS/IMPERS} – DOM possible

[A las alumnas] se felicitó **[a**
 DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL SE_{DOM} congratulate.PST.PRT.3SG DAT=DOM
 las alumnas] (por el rector).
 DEF.F.PL student.F.PL (by DEF.M.SG rector)
 ‘The female students have been congratulated (by the rector).’

As structures similar to (6)b lack an expressed EA, the question is how to explain the presence of DOM. One straightforward hypothesis would be to say that SE (a pronominal-like element after all) itself is merged in Spec, Voice. SE in turn could trigger competition with the object, such that the latter must be differentially marked, if it contains special features. That this is not the right path is demonstrated by various types of data. First, in informal registers, examples such as (7) appear to be possible.⁴ Here SE_{PASS/IMPERS} co-occurs with an unmarked nominal, which triggers agreement on the verb, indicating that it enters into a relationship with T and behaves like a subject. But then, given that the differential marker is otherwise obligatory on animate

³ Some accounts (MacDonald 2017, briefly discussed later) assume that SE can only have an impersonal realization when it allows DOM. The absence of agreement on the verb in (6)b is taken to be the main supporting evidence for the impersonal structure. However, as we will see below, it does not seem to be the case that verbal agreement under SE_{DOM} is not possible.

⁴ Mendikoetxea (2008) attributes ungrammaticality status to examples like (7), under a passive interpretation (if the *by*-phrase is removed, such examples are grammatical as reflexives). The observation seems to be that categories requiring DOM cannot appear as DOM-less subjects under SE_{PASS/IMPERS} with verbal agreement. Our consultants (as well as data from dialectal Spanish) indicate that there is variation when it comes to highly referential classes which are subject to this restriction. For all our informants, what does not seem to be allowed without DOM under SE_{PASS/IMPERS} are the personal pronouns, as seen in (i). We leave aside here an analysis of this restriction (known as the [PERSON] restriction), which is seen in other Romance languages with DOM.

(i) *Se felicitó el (por el rector).
 SE_{PASS/IMPERS} congratulate.PST.3SG he (by DEF.M.SG rector)
 Intended: ‘He was congratulated (by the rector).’

definite objects as in (5), how come it is absent in (7) if the structure contains a subject (SE) which c-commands it and establishes an agreement relation with T? More clearly put, if *las alumnas* in (7) is an object and is c-commanded by a higher nominal (SE), one would predict obligatory DOM, contrary to what we see in the data. This suggests that the presence of DOM in examples such as (6)b is not a matter of competition with SE.

- (7) Se felicitaron las alumnas (por el rector).
 SE_{PASS/(IMPERS)} congratulate.PST3PL DEF.F.PL student.F.PL (by DEF.M.SG rector)
 ‘The students were congratulated (by the rector).’ (*informal, non-standard, dialectal*)

Secondly, there are also speakers who accept examples such as (8), where DOM co-occurs with SE and plural agreement on the verb. This indicates that the probe in T is not satisfied by SE itself, despite its presence in subject position, intervening between T and DOM.

- (8) Se felicitaron a las alumnas (por el rector).
 SE_{DOM} congratulate.PST3PL DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL (by DEF.M.SG rector)
 ‘The students were congratulated (by the rector).’ (*informal, non-standard, dialectal*)

3.1. An implicit argument in SE_{MP/IMP}?

Another possibility to evaluate would be to say that maybe in examples like (6)b there is a pronominal element *pro* in Spec, T and a syntactically projected IA (the agent) in Spec, Voice, as shown schematically in (9).

- (9) ...[TP *pro* T...[VoiceP IA Voice ...[_αP DOM [_α[AccCase]...[VP $\bar{D}\Theta$]]]]

If a *pro*-like element were active in the syntax, it should be detectable by a variety of tests, such as the possibility of hosting depictives, reciprocals, subject-oriented anaphors, etc.⁵ However, these diagnostics do not output grammatical results. Thus, a depictive targeting the putative IA is not possible in (10)a; subject-oriented anaphors (*his*, *self*) tracking the IA are not possible either, as illustrated in (10)b and (10)c. Similarly the goal in (10)d cannot be the IA.⁶ A reciprocal, as in (10)e is ungrammatical too.⁷

(10) Spanish SE_{PASS/IMPERS} – diagnostics targeting the IA in the syntax

- a. *Se felicitó a las alumnas_j orgulloso(s)_i.
 SE_{DOM} congratulate.PST.3SG DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL proud.M.SG/PL
 Intended: ‘The students_j were congratulated proud_i.’ (IA was/were proud)
- b. *Se felicitó a las alumnas_j según su_i deseo.
 SE_{DOM} congratulate.PST.3SG DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL following his wish
 Intended: ‘The students_j were congratulated following his_i/their_i wish.’ (IA’s wish)
- c. *Se felicitó a las alumnas_j por su propio_i interés.

⁵ We use mismatched gender (masculine) on depictives, reciprocals, etc. vs DOM (feminine) to avoid interpretations under which modification applies to DOM, as opposed to the targeted IA.

⁶ In these latter three examples a referential third person interpretation is possible, as long as it is not the IA.

⁷ The same results are obtained for the periphrastic passive, although we cannot include the examples here (for reasons of space). As discussed later in the text, there is independent evidence that the Spanish periphrastic (*be*) passive does not project an IA in the syntax.

- SE_{DOM} congratulate.PST.3SG DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL for his self interest
 Intended: ‘The students_j were congratulated for self_i’s interest.’ (IA’s interest)
- d. *Se felicitó a las alumnas_j por razones
 SE_{DOM} congratulate.PST.3SG DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL for reason.PL
 que le_i beneficiaban.
 that s/he.DAT be beneficial.IMPF.PST.3.PL
 Intended: ‘The students_j were congratulated for reasons that were beneficial to him/her_i’. (beneficial to the IA)
- e. *Se felicitó a las alumnas_j uno_i a otro_i.
 SE_{DOM} congratulate.PST.3SG DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL one.M.SG to other.M.SG
 Intended – literal: ‘The students were congratulated to each other.’
 (i.e., the IAs congratulated each other’s students)

One cannot attribute the ungrammaticality of these examples to the hypothesis that null elements cannot license the categories used as diagnostics here. Spanish is a *pro*-drop language. The silent *pro* of active sentences, licenses them all, as in (11). Table 1 summarizes the results obtained by a comparison of SE_{DOM}, *be* passive and *pro* in active sentences.

(11) Spanish *pro* in active sentences

- a. Felicitó/felicitaron a las alumnas_j orgulloso(s)_i.
 congratulate.PST.3SG/3PL DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL proud.M.SG/PL
 ‘(S)he/they_i congratulated the students_j proud_i.’
- b. Felicitó a las alumnas_j según su_i deseo.
 congratulate.PST.3SG DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL following his wish
 ‘(S)he_i congratulated the students_j according to his/her_i wish.’
- c. Felicitó a las alumnas_j por su propio_i interés.
 congratulate.PST.3SG DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL for his self interest
 ‘(S)he_i congratulated the students_j for his/her_i self interest.’
- d. Felicitó a las alumnas_j por razones que le_i
 congratulate.PST.3SG DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL for reason.PL that s/he.DAT
 beneficiaban.
 be beneficial.IMPF.PST.3.PL
 ‘S/he_i congratulated the students_j for reasons that were beneficial to him/her_i.’
- e. Se Felicitaron a las alumnas_j uno_i a otro_i.
 SE_{RECP} congratulate.PST.3PL DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL one.M.SG to other.M.SG
 ‘They_i congratulated the students_j to each other_i.’

Table 1: IA in syntax: SE_{PASS/IMPERS}, periphrastic passive vs *pro*-drop in active sentences

Test	SE _{PASS/IMPERS} with DOM	periphrastic (<i>be</i>) passive	<i>pro</i> -drop active
depictive	NO	NO	YES
subject-oriented anaphor (<i>su</i>)	NO	NO	YES
subject-oriented anaphor (<i>proprio</i>)	NO	NO	YES
understood goal	NO	NO	YES
reciprocal	NO	NO	YES

Now the question is: are there any other types of tests which might point to the syntactic projection of an IA? A look at the data reveals that agent oriented adverbs such as ‘calmly’, ‘on purpose’, etc. are possible. Similarly, control into certain types of adjuncts goes through. This is seen below; in (12)b the implicit initiator of the congratulating event and of the starting event can be the same.

(12) Spanish adverbials and adjuncts in $SE_{PASS/IMPERS}$

a. Se felicitó a las alumnas con calma.
 SE_{DOM} congratulate.PST.3SG DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL with calm
 ‘The students were congratulated calmly.’

b. Se felicitó a las alumnas antes de inaugurar
 SE_{DOM} congratulate.PST.3SG DAT=DOM DEF.F.PL student.F.PL before of start.INF
 la ceremonia.
 DEF.F.PL ceremony
 ‘The students were congratulated before starting the ceremony.’

However, it has been noticed that agent-oriented PPs and control into adjunct clauses are *not* unambiguous evidence for the *syntactic* projection of the IA (see especially Bhatt and Pancheva 2016 or Pitteroff and Schäfer 2019 for discussion). In Spanish, this is clear from a comparison with periphrastic passives; when it comes to the latter, there is agreement in the literature that they do not have an IA projected in the syntax (for example, one diagnostic by MacDonald 2017 in the next section). The initiator of periphrastic passives can control into adjunct clauses, as seen in (13)b. Agent-oriented adverbials such as *con calma* are possible too, as in (13)a. Remember that DOM is not grammatical on the theme of periphrastic passives.⁸ We agree with the general line in the literature that these tests signal a thematic Voice ($Voice_{[0]}$), that is a type of Voice which semantically selects the thematic role of Agent. What these tests do *not* indicate is the *syntactic projection* of this thematic agent.

(13) Spanish adverbials and control into adjuncts in periphrastic passives

a. Las alumnas fueron felicitadas con calma/con entusiasmo.
 DEF.F.PL student.F.PL be.PST.3PL congratulate.PST.PRT.F.PL with calm/enthusiasm
 ‘The female students were congratulated calmly/with enthusiasm.’

b. Las alumnas fueron felicitadas antes de inaugurar
 DEF.F.PL student.F.PL be.PST.3PL congratulate.PST.PRT.F.PL before of start.INF
 la ceremonia.
 DEF.F.SG ceremony
 ‘The female students were congratulated before initiating the ceremony.’

In conclusion, SE_{DOM} does not give evidence of the syntactic projection of the IA (see also Saab 2014 for similar conclusions). A *by*-phrase is possible, just like with periphrastic passives. The *by*-phrase, however, does not command the object (contrary to predictions in Dependent Case theories as in (2)), does not need obligatory licensing in terms of [uC] (thus, cannot compete for

⁸ $SE_{ANTICAUS}$ does not license these categories, as in (i) - adapted after Mendikoetxea and Battye (2002:167).

(i) *La Ventana se abrió (por sí sola) voluntariamente/para airear la habitación.
 DEF.F.SG window $SE_{ANTICAUS}$ open.PST.3SG by self alone voluntarily/for air out.INF DEF.F.SG building
 ‘The window opened (by itself) voluntarily/to air out the room.’

licensing with the object, contrary to analyses similar to Kalin 2018) and is a PP, and thus cannot give rise to a linearization clash with a DP object (contrary to Richards's 2010 Distinctness Condition in (3)).

Another hypothesis we could entertain is that maybe the type of *pro* seen in SE_{DOM} is structurally reduced (Legate 2014). But then the problem is that some of the diagnostics for the syntactic projection of the IA examined in this section are possible with certain types of SE, for example when a *generic* interpretation arises, and only with certain types of predicates. Generic SE also needs a reduced type of *pro*, as it is not as strong as pronominals seen in *pro-drop* configurations.⁹ One example with a generic SE and the depictive is in (14):

- (14) No se llega borracho a la reunion.
 NEG SE_{GENR} come.3SG.PRES drunk.M.SG to DEF.F.SG meeting
 'One doesn't come drunk to the meeting.' (Spanish)

This indicates that there is an important difference between passive/impersonal and generic SE; only the latter can be assumed to project a reduced type of *pro* in the syntax. However, $SE_{PASS/IMPERS}$ does allow differential object marking.

4. Accusatives without the syntactic projection of the EA

MacDonald (2017) has proposed evidence for the syntactic projection of an IA in SE_{PASS} from a previously unexplored diagnostic, namely inalienable possession. His observations revolve around the contrast in (15), which is taken to indicate that SE_{PASS} in (15)a licenses an inalienable-possession interpretation of a body part DP, contrary to the *be* passive in (15)b.

- (15) Spanish SE_{PASS} vs periphrastic passives: inalienable possession
- a. El profesor hizo una pregunta. Se levantaron
 DEF.M.SG professor make.PST.3SG a.F.SG question. SE_{PASS} raise.PST.3PL
 unas/las manos.
 some.F.PL/DEF.F.PL hand.PL (MacDonald 217: ex.21a)
 'The professor asked a question. Some of the/their hands raised.'
- b. *El profesor hizo una pregunta.
 DEF.M.SG professor make.PST.3SG a.F.SG question
 Unas/las
 some.F.PL/DEF.F.PL
 manos fueron levantadas.
 hand.PL be.PST3PL raise.PST.PRT.F.PL
 'The professor asked a question. Some of their/their hands raised.'

MacDonald (2017) assumes that the inalienable-possession reading can only be obtained if a c-commanding possessor is syntactically present, pragmatics not being enough. The implicit projected external argument serves as the inalienable possessor of the body part in (15)a. As the periphrastic passive in (15)b does not allow an inalienable-possession interpretation of the body part DP, this indicates it does not contain a syntactically projected EA. Thus, while SE_{PASS}

⁹ Examples such (14) are not judged as natural as their *pro-drop* counterparts in active sentences (for some speakers being even ungrammatical). And, in fact, SE_{GENR} might not license all the categories examined in Table 1.

contains a non-referential *pro*, the periphrastic passive lacks *pro* altogether. Both types of passives are, however, thematic (as indicated by the [θ] diacritic).

- (16) a. [VoiceP *pro* Voice_{[θ]se}] → SE_{PASS}/SE_{IMPERS}
 b. [VoiceP Voice_[θ]] → SE_{PASS}/SE_{IMPERS} (MacDonald 2017: ex. 4a, b)

Despite the usefulness of the inalienable possession test in revealing differences between various types of passives, Dobrovie-Sorin (2020) has pointed out independent explanations, which are not related to the presence vs. absence of a syntactically projected IA. As such, these data require further attention. More importantly for our purposes, the test cannot be applied to DOM; inanimate body parts cannot be differentially marked. We have also seen, in Section 3, that there are differences between marked and unmarked arguments (and also the ([PERSON]) restriction in fn. 4). Thus, unless confirmed by unambiguous syntactic tests, it cannot automatically be assumed that SE_{PASS/IMPERS} project the same structure in the context of unmarked vs. marked arguments. For these reasons, we leave the inalienable possession test aside.

As already seen, MacDonald (2017) takes contests with SE_{DOM} to represent a type of impersonal realization (SE_{IMPERS}). This hypothesis is based on two observations in the author's data: i) DOM apparently being only possible with default third person agreement on the verb, and not with full agreement, as in example (6)b; ii) SE_{IMPERS} with DOM not allowing an agent expressed as a *by*-phrase. Although the test based on inalienable possession is not applicable to DOM, MacDonald (2017) follows Rivero (2002) in the assumption that SE_{IMPERS} contains a syntactically projected implicit argument. Rivero (2002) discussed data with impersonal interpretations as in (17) where SE allows binding into a passive complement, a property which is traditionally taken to require the syntactic presence of an implicit EA (Jaeggli 1986).

- (17) Spanish SE_{IMPERS}: control into passive complements
 Siempre *se* quiere ser admirado/appreciado.
 always SE want.3SG be.INF admire.PST.PRT/appreciate.PST.PRT
 'One always wants to be admired/appreciated.' (Rivero 2002: ex. 15a, p.9; adapted)

However, neither examples such as (17) provide indication that SE_{DOM} contains a syntactically projected EA. First, the complement embedded by SE is a periphrastic passive which, as we have seen (cf. (6)a), does not allow DOM. Second, it is not clear that we are not dealing with a *generic* realization of SE in these configurations; we have seen in (14) that generics need to be kept separate from passives and impersonals.¹⁰ And third, we have also seen, that the two properties assumed by MacDonald (2017) to characterize SE with DOM (his SE_{IMPERS}), namely default agreement and lack of *by*-phrase, do not hold for all the speakers. As a result, examples like (17) too have to be set aside too.

Given that we cannot unambiguously prove the syntactic presence of the implicit arguments in SE_{DOM}, we side with non-projectionist accounts. As shown in (18), although SE_{DOM} is thematic, it does not project a specifier hosting a syntactically present external argument (the agent).

- (18) [VoiceP Voice_[θ]] → SE_{DOM}

¹⁰ And, in fact, at least some of the diagnostics listed in Table 1 do go through in this context.

Then we adapt some recent observations in Šereskaitė (2020) who has discussed an active existential from Lithuanian where Voice checks accusative case in the absence of a syntactically projected IA in Spec, Voice. The constructions under investigation here similarly motivate the conclusion that accusative Case can be licensed in the absence of a syntactically projected implicit argument in Spec, Voice.

However, the type of differentially marked arguments addressed in this paper appear to have a more complex structure than unmarked accusatives. Following the remarks in Irimia (2020, in press), we assume that DOM contains additional discourse (δ)-related features (grammaticalized animacy that is relevant in the discourse, specificity, etc.), beyond (uninterpretable) Case. Assuming the presence of both v and Voice (following Legate 2014), we propose that the locus of accusative Case licensing in these constructions is v . The additional δ -feature in differentially marked objects is licensed by a separate functional projection, in the mid verbal field, as schematically shown in (19). This head is abbreviated as α , for convenience; following López (2012); Pancheva and Zubizarreta (2018), this functional projection collapses aspect, viewpoint or sentience specifications. In our view, DOM is not dependent on the presence of a c-commanding element in the syntax; it is, in fact, dependent on whether the relevant configuration contains a locus where discourse-related features can be properly licensed, beyond the uninterpretable Case.¹¹

The periphrastic passive, as in (13), contains a type of v which cannot license accusative Case. Therefore, differential marking is not possible. The following two sections briefly illustrate two other languages, Hindi-Urdu and Moldovan, which raise the same problem as Spanish – they permit DOM in structures where the syntactic projection of an implicit external argument cannot be demonstrated.

5. DOM and passives in Hindi-Urdu

Just like Spanish, Hindi (Indo-Aryan) is a language with robust DOM (Comrie 1985, 1989; Mahajan 1989; Masica 1991; Mohanan 2001; Bhatt and Anagnostopoulou 1996; Bhatt 2005; Butt 2006, a.o.). Higher animates as well as nominals with specific interpretation are introduced

¹¹ This analysis can easily derive well-known *syntactic* properties of DOM, not discussed here: their presence in a higher position than unmarked objects (López 2012 for Spanish, Bhatt and Anagnostopoulou 1996 for Hindi Urdu, a.o.), syntactic co-occurrence restrictions (Ormazabal and Romero 2013 for Spanish, Irimia in press for Romanian, etc.), interactions with accusative clitic doubling (as briefly seen for Moldovan in section 6), etc.

(22) Hindi DOM not possible on subjects of unaccusatives

raam-(***ko**) gir/mar ga-yaa.
 Ram-DAT=DOM fall/die go-PFV.M.SG
 Intended: ‘Ram fell/died.’

(23) Hindi DOM: purpose adverbials and control into adjuncts

a. aurat-**ko** jaan-buujh-kar giraftaar ki-yaa ga-yaa
 woman-DAT=DOM on-purpose arrest do-PASS.M.SG go-PFV.M.SG
 ‘The woman was arrested on purpose.’ (The IA did it on purpose.)

b. aurat-**ko** promotion paane-ke liye giraftaar ki-yaa ga-yaa
 woman-DAT=DOM promotion receive-GEN for arrest do-PASS.M.SG go-PFV.M.SG
 ‘The woman was arrested to receive a promotion.’ (The IA wanted a promotion.)

Depictive-like elements seem to be possible; however, native speakers mention that only the non-inflected form of the adjectives is allowed. This begs the question of whether these are not, in fact, adverbials modifying the event, similarly to ‘on purpose’ in (23)a. As such, they would not automatically entail the syntactic presence of an EA.

(24) Hindi passive DOM and event modification

a. aurat-**ko** piye-hue giraftar ki-yaa ga-yaa
 woman- DAT=DOM drunk arrest do-PASS.M.SG go-PFV.M.SG
 ‘The woman was arrested drunk.’ (Either the woman or the agent was drunk.)

b. siita-**ko** nange paḍ pakr-aa ga-yaa
 Sita-DAT=DOM naked feet catch-PASS.M.SG go-PFV.M.SG
 ‘Sita was caught barefoot.’ (Either Sita or the catcher was barefoot.)

On the other hand, there are various diagnostics which do not confirm the syntactic projection of an IA. For example, the native speakers consulted do not allow *by*-phrases (built on the instrumental) in these passives (no matter whether the object is marked or unmarked). Passives formed with the Sanskrit *dwaaraa* are similarly rejected, due to their marginality:

(25) Hindi passive DOM and *by*-phrases

a. *siitaa-**ko** raam-se dekh-aa ga-yaa
 Sita-DAT=DOM Ram-INST see-PASS.M.SG go-PFV.M.SG
 Intended: ‘Sita was seen by Ram.’

b. *siitaa-**ko** raam dwaaraa dekh-aa ga-yaa
 Sita-DAT=DOM Ram DWAARAA see-PASS.M.SG go-PFV.M.SG
 Intended: ‘Sita was seen by Ram.’

Let’s see now whether a *self*-reflexive (‘apne’) can be bound by the IA. The answer given by the consultants is negative. The sentence in (26)a cannot mean that the knife belongs to the implicit EA or to some other third entity. The implicit EA is not available in (26)b nor (26)c either. In (26)b and (26)c, the third person pronominal *uske* can track DOM or some other third person entity which is not the implicit EA.

- (26) Hindi passive DOM: *self* and personal pronoun (j = implicit agent, k = someone else)
- a. **balban_i-ko** **apne_{i/*j}** **chaaku-se** **maar-aa** **ga-yaa**
 Balban-DAT=DOM self.GEN-OBL knife-INS hit-PASS.M.SG go-PFV.M.SG
 Intended: ‘Balban_i was stabbed with his_j own knife.’
- b. **balban_i-ko** **uske_{i/*j/k}/apne_{i/*j/*k}** **office** **bulaa-yaa** **ga-yaa.**
 Balban-DAT=DOM 3SG/self.GEN-OBL office call-PASS.M.SG go-PFV.M.SG
 Intended: ‘Balban_i was summoned to his_j/his_j own office.’
- c. **sita_i-ko** **uske_{i/*j/k}/apne_{i/*j/*k}** **fayde-ke** **liye** **gumrah** **ki-yaa**
 Sita-DAT=DOM 3SG/self.GEN-OBL benefit-GEN for deceit do-PASS.M.SG
ga-yaa
go-PFV.M.SG
 Intended: ‘Sita_i was deceived for her_j/her_j own benefit.’

Further doubt that the DOM passive contains an IA in Spec, Voice comes from the syntactic behaviour of DOM. The data indicate that DOM in passives behaves like a subject in that it can bind the possessor anaphor *apnaa*. But it is not entirely subject-like in that it can also bind possessor pronouns, as we have also seen in the examples above. This result is as expected. Under our assumption that DOM involves licensing by an additional discourse-linked functional head in the absence of a *pro* IA in Spec, Voice, it should be the case that DOM passes objecthood diagnostics. However, as we will also see in Moldovan, DOM licensing does not prevent its raising to a higher Spec, position. This operation is presumably related to the need of a higher sentential licenser. But If Spec, Voice contained *pro* (which is not featureless), it is not clear why it would get skipped, DOM being targeted instead.

In (27), just like in (26)a, we see passive DOM’s possibility to control the anaphor *apnaa*. In (28), we see this possibility is allowed for subjects of actives, but not for objects.

- (27) **siitaa-ko** **apn-e** **ghar-me** **pakR-aa** **ga-yaa**
 Sita-DAT=DOM self.GEN-M.OBL house-LOC catch-PASS.M.SG go-PFV.M.SG
 ‘Sita_i was caught in her_i house.’
 (Hindi-Urdu)
- (28) **raam-ne** **Siitaa-ko** **apn-e** **ghar-me** **pakR-aa**
 Ram-ERG Sita-DAT=DOM self.GEN-M.OBL house-LOC catch-PFV.M.SG
 ‘Ram_i caught Sita_j in his_i/*her_j house.’
 (Hindi-Urdu)

Subjects, on the other hand, cannot control possessor pronouns, which can be bound by some other argument, or stay free, as in (29) or (30), the latter from the NOM-ACC alignment.

- (29) **raam-ne** **siitaa-ko** **us-k-e** **ghar-me** **pakR-aa.**
 Ram-ERG Sita-DAT=DOM 3SG-GEN-OBL house-LOC catch-PFV.M.SG
 ‘Ram_i caught Sita_j in his/her_{j/k}/*_i house.’
 (Hindi-Urdu)
- (30) **raam** **siitaa-ko** **us-k-e** **ghar-me** **pakaR-taa** **thaa**
 Ram Sita-DAT=DOM 3SG-GEN-OBL house-LOC catch-IMPF.M.SG PST.M.SG
 ‘Ram_i used to catch Sita_j in his/her_{j/k}/*_i house.’
 (Hindi-Urdu)

As expected, the restriction on controlling possessor pronouns holds with non-DOM passives. As we see in (31), non-DOM arguments cannot bind possessor pronouns in passives.

- (31) *siitaa us-k-e ghar-me pakR-ii ga-ii.*
 Sita 3SG-GEN-M.OBL house-LOC catch-PASS.F.SG go-PFV.F.SG
 ‘Sita_i was caught in his/her_{k/*i} house.’ (Hindi-Urdu)

However, this restriction does not hold with DOM in passives; the latter can bind possessor pronouns, as already seen in (26); another example is provided in (32):

- (32) *siitaa-ko us-k-e ghar-me pakR-aa ga-yaa.*
 Sita-DAT=DOM 3SG-GEN-M.OBL house-LOC catch-PASS.M.SG go-PFV.M.SG
 ‘Sita_i was caught in his/her_{i/j} house.’ (Hindi-Urdu)

In conclusion, the Hindi data illustrate the following: i) DOM in passives is both subject-like and object-like syntactically; ii) there is no unambiguous evidence supporting the syntactic projection of an IA. Just like for Spanish, we find problems with theories which relate DOM to the syntactic projection of an EA for accusative case to be assigned. We have proposed, instead, that DOM is not a matter of competition with subject licensing; DOM is possible even if an EA is not syntactically projected in Spec, Voice. As long as a type of *v* which checks accusative case is present, together with a functional projection which can license discourse-related specifications (as in (19)), DOM is possible.

6. DOM and the supine in Moldovan

The last language we examine is Moldovan (Romanian spoken in the Republic of Moldova). The data under interest are in (33); (33)a contains as the main verb the modal *trebuie* ‘must/it is necessary’, which cannot inflect for person and number, being instead restricted only to 3rd person singular morphology. This modal embeds the so-called ‘supine’, which in Moldovan (just like in Romanian, see especially Soare 2002, 2007; or Pană Dindelegan (ed.): 233) is composed of a prepositional element (in this case, *de*) and a *non-inflected* form (cf. (33)c) of the past participle (Sandfeld and Olsen 1936: 281; Marin et al. 1998: 115-116; Gabinschi 2010; Dragomirescu and Hill 2014; Dragomirescu 2015; Dragomirescu and Nicolae 2016; Hill and Alboiu 2016: 292-295; Costea 2021, a.o. for details about the Moldovan supine). As also emphasized in the literature, (33)a allows only an arbitrary/impersonal interpretation and a lexical subject is strictly ungrammatical, as in (33)b.

- (33) Moldovan supine and DOM
- a. *Trebu(ie)*¹³ *de(-i) ajutat pe cei mai slabi.*
 must.3SG SUP-(CL.3.M.PL.ACC) help.PST.PRT LOC=DOM those more weak.M.PL
 ‘One should/must help the weaker ones.’ (adapted after Costea 2021)
- b. *(*Oamenii) trebuie (*oamenii) de-i (*oamenii)*
 people.M.PL must.3SG people.M.PL SUP-(CL.3M.PL.ACC) people.M.PL
*ajutat (*oamenii) pe cei mai slabi.*
 help.PST.PRT people.M.PL LOC=DOM those more weak.M.PL
 Intended: ‘People should help the weaker ones.’
- c. **Trebu(ie) de ajutați pe cei mai slabi.*
 must.3SG SUP help.PST.PRT.M.PL LOC=DOM those more weak.M.PL

¹³ As Costea (2021) also notices, many speakers use the shorter form *trebu*. The orthography of the examples has been simplified.

The puzzle has at its center the direct object, which is differentially marked, as it is animate (and also contains a demonstrative). Animacy-based DOM is robust in Moldovan, just like in standard Romanian (see especially Hill and Mardale 2021 for Daco-Romance DOM), and uses a locative maker. Moreover, the differentially marked nominal can also be clitic doubled using the accusative form of the clitic.¹⁴ The presence of the clitic, DOM topicalization, as well as the uninflected morpheme *ca*¹⁵ in (34) are a strong indication that the Moldovan supine projects a CP structure - see especially Costea (2021) whom we follow in labelling the construction the *clausal de-supine*. However, despite its clausal structure, the supine cannot function as an independent main clause; the sentence in (35) is ungrammatical, regardless of whether the overt subject is removed.

(34) Trebu(ie) *ca* **pe** cei mai slabi mereu *de-i* ajutat.
 must SBJV DOM those more weak.M.PL always SUP-CL.3M.PL.ACC help,PST.PRT
 ‘One should always help the weaker ones.’ (Moldovan, adapted from Costea 2021: ex.1)

(35) *[Oamenii] *ca* **pe** cei slabi [oamenii] *de-i*
 people.DEF.M.PL SBJV DOM those weak.M.PL people.DEF.M.PL SUP-CL.3M.PL.ACC
 ajutat.
 help.PST.PRT
 Intended: ‘People/one to help the weak ones.’ (Moldovan)

6.1. An implicit argument in Moldovan supine?

However, despite the presence of an extended clausal spine with the supine, the application of various texts indicates the absence of a syntactically projected implicit EA in Spec, Voice. This conclusion is strengthened by a comparison with other configurations with non-expressed agents. Across Daco-Romance, another construction with an implicit agent/initiator is the one using the Pan-Romance SE clitic, which we have already seen for Spanish in sections 2 & 3. Daco-Romance SE can construct medio-passives, impersonals, anti-causatives, etc. (see especially Dobrovie Sorin 1998, 2021, etc. for Romanian SE). The sentences in (36) illustrate a generic impersonal realization of SE which allows a depictive and a reciprocal tracking the IA.¹⁶ This might indicate that an IA is syntactically projected in these examples. In (37) we see a passive SE interpretation which is possible with a *by*-phrase.

(36) Moldovan - SE_{GENR}
 a. Nu se vine la noi *beat*.
 NEG SE_{GENR} come.3SG.PRES at we drunk.M.SG
 ‘One doesn’t come to our place drunk.’
 b. Se merge *de la unu’ la altu’*.
 SE_{GENR} go.3SG.PRES of at one.DEF.M.SG at other.DEF.M.SG
 Lit. ‘One goes from one to the other.’ (from one’s place to the other’s)

¹⁴ In Moldovan, similarly to standard Romanian only DOM can be clitic doubled, and not unmarked objects.

¹⁵ Which in Daco-Romance is seen with subjunctives.

¹⁶ Just like what we have seen in Spanish, other types of SE (anti-causative, etc.) do not allow these elements.

not appear to be syntactically projected in *clausal de-supine*.

Although less studied both empirically and formally, Moldovan *clausal de-supine* allows DOM in the absence of a syntactically projected IA, providing further support for theories which do not link the accusative to the presence of a higher c-commanding nominal (recent discussion in Šereskaitė 2020). Similarly to what we have proposed for Spanish in section 4 (and for Hindi in section 5), Moldovan contains a type of v which can check accusative case. DOM, however, involves the presence of additional discourse-related features, beyond Case. A functional projection with discourse specifications is activated in the mid vP , licensing the differential object, as in (19). Thus, once again, what matters is the possibility of licensing the special features in DOM by discourse-related functional projections which act in tandem with accusative Case assigning v . This licensing mechanism is independent of the syntactic presence of a higher c-commanding nominal.

Moldovan *de-supine* also illustrates a novel observation, namely that even accusative clitic doubling on DOM is possible in the absence of a syntactically projected EA. Moreover, placement of DOM in a preverbal position is not blocked either, as seen in (34).

Table 2: SE and *clausal de-supine* in Moldovan

DIAGNOSTIC	SE _{GENR} ; SE _{PASS}	Clausal de-supine
IA-oriented depictive	SE _{GENR} - \checkmark	*
reciprocal	SE _{GENR} - \checkmark	*
<i>by</i> -phrase	SE _{PASS} - \checkmark	*
Inalienably possessed DP	SE _{PASS} - \checkmark	*/??

7. Conclusions

Recent discussions have reiterated the observation that accusative case can be assigned in the absence of a syntactically projected EA (Šereskaitė 2020, a.o.); this conclusion is problematic for accounts stemming from Comrie (1989) or Burzio's Generalization, under which accusative morphology is simply the means to distinguish subjects from objects. The data we have analyzed in this paper involve differentially marked objects in passives and impersonals which lack an expressed EA, from three languages: Spanish, Hindi-Urdu and Moldovan. Through an examination of a variety of diagnostics, we have shown that an implicit EA projected in the syntax cannot be motivated either. Thus, the special morphology in differentially marked objects is *not* a means to distinguish objects from subjects. We have proposed an analysis under which DOM, which involves the presence of additional discourse-linking features beyond [uC], needs licensing by a functional projection with discourse properties in the mid vP domain. Only those configurations in which v can check [uC] and also contain the additional discourse related projection allow DOM, irrespectively of whether the implicit EA is projected in the syntax or not.

References

- Aissen, Judith. 2003. Differential object marking: Iconicity vs. economy, *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory* 21 (3): 435–483.
- Baker, Mark C. 2015. *Case: Its principles and parameters*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Bhatt, Rajesh. 2003. Passivization. Handout from lecture notes on *Topics in the syntax of*

- modern Indo-Aryan languages.*
- Bhatt, Rajesh. 2005. Long distance agreement in Hindu Urdu. *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory* 34(4): 757–807.
- Bhatt, Rajesh and Elena Anagnostopoulou. 1996. Object shift and specificity: evidence from *ko-* phrases in Hindi. In Lisa M. Dobrin, Kora Singer and Lisa McNair (eds.), *Papers from the 32nd Regional Meeting of the Chicago Linguistic Society*, 11–22. Chicago: Chicago Linguistic Society.
- Bhatt, Rajesh and Roumyana Pancheva. 2006. Implicit arguments. In Martin Everaert and Henk van Riemsdijk (eds.), *The Wiley Blackwell Companion to syntax. Second edition*, 554–584. Blackwell.
- Bossong, Georg. 1991. Differential Object Marking in Romance and beyond. In Dieter Wanner and Douglas Kibbee (eds.), *New Analyses in Romance Linguistics: Selected Papers from the XVIII Linguistic Symposium on Romance Languages*, 143–170. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Bossong, Georg. 1998. Le marquage différentiel de l'objet dans les langues d'Europe. In Jack Feuillet (ed.), *Actance et valence dans les langues de l'Europe*, 259–294. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Burzio, Luigi. 1986. *Italian syntax*. Dordrecht: D. Reidel Publishing Company.
- Butt, Miriam. 2006. *Theories of case*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Comrie, Bernard. 1984. Reflections on verb agreement in Hindi and related languages. *Linguistics* 23(1): 143–146.
- Comrie, Bernard. 1989. *Language universals and linguistic typology*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Costea, Ștefania. 2021. Clausal de-supine in Moldovan. The state of the art. Ms.
- Dobrovie Sorin, Carmen. 1998. Impersonal SE in romance and the passivization of unergatives. *Linguistic Inquiry* 29: 399–439
- Dobrovie Sorin, Carmen. 2021. Implicit agents and the Person Constraint on SE-passives. In Grant Armstrong and Jonaton MacDonald (eds.), *Unraveling the complexity of the SE clitic*, 111–135. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-57004-0_5
- Dragomirescu, Adina. 2015. Utilizări dialectale ale supinului. In Rodica Zafiu, Ioana Nedelcu (eds), *Variația lingvistică: probleme actuale. Actele celui de al 14-lea Colocviu al Departamentului de Lingvistică*, București, Editura Universității din București, 39–48.
- Dragomirescu, Adina and Virginia Hill. 2014. *A diachronic perspective on de-supine complements* (paper presented at ACED, University of Bucharest, 5–7 june 2014).
- Dragomirescu, Adina and Alexandru Nicolae. 2016. Originea formelor verbale „nonfinite” cu flexiune: infinitiv vs supin. *Diacronia* 4: 1–16.
- Fábregas, Antonio. 2013. Differential object marking in Spanish. The state of the art. *Borealis* 2/2: 1–80.
- Gabinschi, Marcu 2010. Formele verbale nepredicative nonconjunctivale ale limbii române (pe marginea tratării lor în gramatica oficială). Chișinău: Institutul de filologie al AȘM.
- Hill, Virginia and Gabriela Alboiu. 2016. *Verb Movement and Clause Structure in Old Romanian*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Irimia, Monica Alexandrina. 2020. Types of structural objects: Some remarks on differential object marking in Romanian. In András Bányi & Laura Kalin (eds.), *Case, Agreement, and Their Interactions: New Perspectives on Differential Argument Marking*, 77–126. Boston/Berlin: de Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110666137-003>
- Irimia, Monica Alexandrina. in press. Oblique differential object marking and types of nominals. *Canadian Journal of Linguistics*.

- Jaeggli, Osvald. 1986. Passive. *Linguistic Inquiry* 17: 587-622.
- Kalin, Laura. 2018. Licensing and differential object marking: the view from Neo-Aramaic. *Syntax* 21 (2): 112-159.
- Kidwai, Sana. 2020. Accusative case and the verbal domain in Hindi Urdu. Handout of presentation at University of Cambridge Syntax Lab, 2 June 2020. https://www.mml.cam.ac.uk/files/handout_kidwai_june_2020.pdf
- Lavine, James. 2010. Case and events in transitive impersonals. *Journal of Slavic Linguistics* 18: 101-130.
- Legate, Julie. 2014. *Voice and v in Acehnese*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Levin, Ted and Omer Preminger. 2015. Case in Sakha: are two modalities really necessary? *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory* 33 (1): 231-250.
- López, Luis. 2012. Indefinite objects: scrambling, choice functions and differential marking. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- MacDonald, Jonathan E. 2017. An Implicit Projected Argument in Spanish Impersonal- and Passive-Se Constructions. *Syntax* 4: 353-383.
- Majahan, Anoop. 1989. Agreement and agreement phrases. In Itziar Laka and Anoup Kumar Mahajan (eds.), *Functional heads and clause structure*, 217-252. Cambridge, MA: MIT Working Papers in Linguistics. No. 10.
- Mahajan, Anoop. 2010. Oblique subjects and Burzio's generalization. In Eric Reuland (ed.), *Arguments and case. Explaining Burzio's Generalization*, 79-102. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing.
- Marantz, Alec. 1991. Case and licensing. In German Westphal, Benjamin Ao and Hee-Rahk Chae (eds.), *Proceedings of the 8th Eastern States Conference on Linguistics (ESCOL 8)*, 234-253, Ithaca, NY: CLC Publications.
- Marin, Maria, Mărgărit, Iulia and Neagoe Victorela. 1998. Graiuri românești din Ucraina și Republica Moldova. *Fonetică și dialectologie* 17: 69-155.
- Masica, Colin. 1991. *The Indo-Iranian languages*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Mendikoetxea, Amaya. 2008. Clitic impersonal constructions in Romance: Syntactic features and semantic interpretation. *Transactions of the Philological Society* 106:290-336.
- Mendikoetxea, Amaya and Adrian Battye. 2002. Arb *SE/SI* in transitive contexts: a comparative study. *Rivista di grammatica generativa* 15: 161-195.
- Mohanan, Tara. 2001. *Argument structure in Hindi-Urdu*. Stanford: CSLI Publications.
- Ormazabal, Javier and Juan Romero. 2013. Differential object marking, case and agreement. *Borealis: An International Journal of Hispanic Linguistics* 2(2): 221-239. <https://doi.org/10.7557/1.2.2.2808>.
- Pană Dindelegan, Gabriela (ed.). 2013. *The Grammar of Romanian*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Pancheva, Roumyana and María Luisa Zubizarreta. 2018. The Person Case Constraint. The syntactic encoding of perspective. *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory* 36(4). 1291-1337. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007%2Fs11049-017-9395-7>
- Pitteroff, Marcel, and Florian Schäfer. 2019. Implicit control crosslinguistically. *Language* 95:136-184. <https://doi.org/10.1353/lan.2019.0016>.
- Richards, Norvin. 2010. *Uttering trees*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Rivero, Maria Luisa. 2002. On impersonal reflexives in Romance and Slavic and semantic variation. In Joaquim Camps and Caroline R. Wiltshire (eds.), *Romance Syntax, Semantics and L2 Acquisition: Selected papers from the 30th Linguistic Symposium on Romance Languages 2000*, 169-197. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.

- Saab, Andrs. 2014. Syntax or nothing: Some theoretical and empirical remarks on implicit arguments. *Borealis: An International Journal of Hispanic Linguistics* 3(2):125–183.
- Sandfeld, Kristian and Hedvig Olsen. 1936. *Syntaxe roumaine. Emploi des mots  flexion*. Paris: E. Droz.
- Šereskait, Milena. 2020. Active existential in Lithuanian. Remarks on Burzio’s Generalization. *Linguistic Inquiry* 1-46. Early access.
- Soare, Elena. 2002. *Le supin roumain et la thorie des catgories mixtes*. PhD dissertation. Universit de Paris 7 Denis Diderot - ANRT Lille.
- Soare, Elena. 2007. Morphosyntactic Mismatches Revised: the Case of Romanian Supine. *Acta Linguistica Hungarica* 54: 1–19.
- de Swart, Peter. 2007. *Crosslinguistic variation in object marking*. Utrecht: LOT Publications
- Torrego, Esther. 1998. *The dependencies of objects*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Wood, Jim. 2017. The accusative-subject generalization. *Syntax* 20: 249–291.